

DMP for Microbiome Research of 16S rRNA Sequences from Ticks

Version 0

Description

This Data Management Plan describes how research data generated within the ERDF project No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001 will be managed. The project supports doctoral research grants (ANM_K_DG_06 and ANM_K_DG_26) implemented in 2024 and 2025. The research focuses on tick-borne pathogens and microbiome analysis. In 2024, tick specimens were collected from domestic dogs, and in 2025 from wild birds.

The project generates molecular data (16S rRNA sequencing data), associated metadata (host species, tick species, developmental stage, sampling region), and bioinformatic and statistical analysis outputs.

This DMP outlines procedures for data collection, storage, security, documentation, and long-term preservation, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles. Research data will be deposited in Zenodo, with access conditions (open, embargoed, or restricted) depending on publication status.

Funder

European Union's Recovery and Resilience Mechanism

Grant

Consolidation of the Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis and the Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre

Researchers

Agne Namiņa

Organizations

Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [DMP for Microbiome Research of 16S rRNA Sequences from Ticks](#)

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

[Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Union's Recovery and Resilience Mechanism](#)

Grants: [Consolidation of the Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis and the Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre](#)

Project: [Cite Project](#)

3. License

License:

Access Rights: [Restricted](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

16S rRNA sequences of tick microbiome

This dataset includes raw 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing data generated from tick microbiome samples. Tick specimens were collected from domestic dogs in 2024 and from wild birds in 2025 within doctoral research supported by the ERDF-funded project No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001.

Raw sequencing data are stored in BAM format as generated by the sequencing platform. Processed data include FASTQ files (where applicable), taxonomic assignment tables (OTU/ASV tables), diversity indices, and statistical analysis outputs (R scripts and figures).

Associated metadata include host species (dog or bird), tick species, developmental stage, and sampling region. No personal data are included.

The purpose of the dataset is to characterize tick-associated microbial communities and assess the presence of tick-borne pathogens.

Data are stored on secure institutional servers and will be deposited in Zenodo. Depending on publication status, access may initially be restricted or embargoed. Metadata will remain publicly available in accordance with FAIR principles.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data consist of 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing results from tick microbiome samples. Ticks were collected from domestic dogs in 2024 and from wild birds in 2025. The purpose of the data generation is to characterize tick-associated microbial communities and to investigate potential associations between microbiome composition and the presence of tick-borne pathogens, including *Borrelia* spp. and other relevant agents. The data support the objectives of the doctoral research conducted within the ERDF-funded project.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Raw NGS sequencing data (BAM files) and processed microbiome analysis datasets

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

BAM (raw sequencing data), FASTQ (derived reads), CSV/TSV (processed tables), R scripts (.R), PDF/TIFF (figures)

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

15-20

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The dataset consists of newly generated primary sequencing data obtained within the project. Existing public datasets on tick microbiomes were reviewed during the study design phase; however, due to differences in geographic origin, host species, and ecological conditions, previously published datasets were not directly suitable for addressing the research objectives. Therefore, new data were generated to specifically characterize tick microbiomes under Latvian environmental conditions.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The dataset may be useful for researchers studying tick microbiomes, vector-borne pathogens, host-microbiome interactions, and ecological differences in Northern and Baltic regions. The data contribute to understanding tick-associated microbial diversity under Latvian environmental conditions and may support comparative studies at regional and international levels.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Darwin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Darwin Core; NCBI Taxonomy

<https://dwc.tdwg.org/>

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Data and metadata are planned to be deposited in a public repository after publication of the related scientific article.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data are currently not publicly accessible as they are intended for publication in a peer-reviewed scientific article. Access may be granted upon reasonable request to the authors prior to publication.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

Comment:

Data will be made publicly available after publication of the related scientific article.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

GenBank

NCBI is an internationally recognized repository for nucleotide sequence data and ensures long-term preservation and accessibility.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Raw sequencing data (BAM/FASTQ files) can be accessed and processed using standard open-source bioinformatics tools such as SAMtools and QIIME2. No proprietary software is required.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

Data analysis methods will be described in detail in the related scientific publication.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Data will be provided in standard open formats (BAM/FASTQ) commonly used in high-throughput sequencing. These formats are widely supported by open-source bioinformatics software and allow integration with other publicly available sequence datasets.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

SILVA ribosomal RNA gene database

<https://www.arb-silva.de>

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Other (Public Domain)

Data will be made publicly available through NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under the repository's standard terms, ensuring free and open access for research purposes.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2047-12-31

Data will become reusable once they are publicly released in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) following publication. The repository ensures long-term preservation and continued accessibility.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Costs related to data management, storage and preparation for repository submission were covered within the project budget. Public deposition of sequencing data in NCBI SRA does not require additional fees.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Agne Namiņa

Project leaderr is responsible for data management, including data storage, quality control, metadata preparation and submission to public repositories.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Long-term data preservation will be ensured by the selected public repository (NCBI SRA), which provides sustainable archiving without additional cost to the project.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Raw sequencing data and metadata are stored on password-protected computers and secure servers with regular backup procedures. Access is restricted to authorized project members during the project period.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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